

IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN
FORMATION OF LIBRARY CULTURE

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada bolalarni kitobga qiziqtirish, kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish va bu borada ota-onalarning oʻrni haqidagi fikrlar yoritilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalar, kitobxonlik madaniyati, bilim, shakllantirish, maʼnaviyat, maʼrifat, kitob, inson, hayot.

Аннотация. В данной статье освещены вопросы развития интереса у детей к книге, формирования культуры чтения и роли родителей в этом вопросе.

Ключевые слова: дошкольники старшего возраста, культура чтения, знания, становление, духовность, просвещение, книга, личность, жизнь.

Annotation. This article covers ideas about the interest of children in books, the formation of a culture of reading and the role of parents in this regard.

Key words: preschool older children, reading culture, knowledge, formation, spirituality, enlightenment, book, man, life.

If we look at the history of the development and progress of society and the nation, the place of educated, spiritual and enlightened youth in the development of society is incomparable. Books are considered to be one of the main factors that educate such young people - a means of reading.

"Life is the dream of every heart, and a book is a life for someone who knows its value," says H.H. Niaziy. If we look at the history of the development and progress of society and the nation, the place of educated, spiritual and enlightened youth in the development of society is incomparable. Books are considered to be one of the main factors that educate such young people - a means of reading. The book is the most unique discovery created by mankind, which lifts us from the earth to the sky, leads us to perfection, brings light and warmth to the hearts of people, helps us to consciously understand the difference between white and black, good and evil, destruction and creativity. .

The book glorifies man, teaches human qualities such as love for the Motherland, philanthropy, looking with gratitude at the life he lives, being kind and polite to others, and sharing goodness with the people around him.

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The importance of the book in human life is incomparable, it is an inextinguishable light that illuminates the paths of human life, a source of happiness that gives meaning to human life, a loyal friend that accompanies in any situation.

Taking into account these aspects, today, systematic work is being carried out to increase interest in books and the level of reading among young people and the population, and to widely promote reading.

In the process of wide implementation of reading in practice, first of all, we can reconstruct the existing libraries, update their material and technical base, provide necessary scientific and literary literature, widely introduce modern innovative technologies in the activities of libraries and use them effectively. Necessary measures for the implementation of these works have been determined and their implementation is regularly monitored. As a clear proof of this, the 5 important initiatives in the development of our country, "Raising the spirituality of young people, organizing systematic work on wide promotion of reading among them" is a clear example of our opinion.

Our great-grandfathers also emphasized that the book has a great role in the upbringing of children, that it is necessary to value it as an inexhaustible wing of thinking, enriching the spiritual world of a person, as a highly creative and creative tool, and to use it effectively. Experts called the first young period of a child's life "the age of miracles" [3, p. 165].

During this period, children are prepared to read books. First of all, they should learn the skills of speaking, listening and speaking perfectly. The process of forming children's interest in books will give a very positive result if we start with the family, and then the expected result can be more effective if we continue to cooperate with the family in preschool educational organizations.

As all criteria of education are formed in the family, reading culture will have good results if it starts from this place. Because it is not for nothing that it is said, "A bird does what it sees in its nest."

In the holy place, it is good for parents to be role models and to read books themselves in order to increase children's interest in books. If the parents in the family love books, then the child raised in such a family will also be familiar with books, such children will have a wide worldview, a wide range of thinking, polite, kind, try to do good to others as much as possible, every word they say He will grow up to be an intelligent child who thinks about what he is doing, in a word, tries to show the qualities of a perfect personality.

The systematic conduct of reading in a family environment increases the effectiveness of the expected result. Telling children about Uzbek folk tales from a

young age inculcates human qualities such as hard work, sincerity, hospitality, as well as concepts such as respect and reverence for national and universal values.

In addition, we introduce our thinkers such as Alisher Navoi, Farobi, Abdulla Avloni, Niazi, Yusuf Khos Khajib, Jalaluddin Rumi, and their educational ideas serve as the main source in child education [2, 27- b.].

The President of our Republic also emphasized that the role and importance of books in the education of the young generation is incomparable, "At the same time, while mastering the latest achievements in the field of information and communication, we must increase the interest of young people in reading books, it is necessary to pay special attention to making friends with books, to further increase the reading level of the population", his opinions are proof of our opinion [1, p. 27].

Based on the above, we can recommend the following to parents:

- be an example to make the child interested in books;
- read examples from the book you read or tell a story;
- choose age-appropriate thoughts for the child to speak;
- create a family library, create a separate section for the child;
- choose and buy books suitable for the age of the child;
- regularly read to your child a few poems, children's poems with repeated lines, picture books, various stories and fairy tales;
- occasionally take children to the library and bookstore;
- let the books you choose meet the pedagogical and psychological requirements.

In short, the basis of all good works and creative ideas is a book. It is also a book that shines the light of knowledge on us. That's why today, if we start the interest in books from the family and for this, we will create age-appropriate libraries for them. On the basis of the formation of reading skills in children, it is necessary to develop oral speech and increase love for books.

If we start from the family to rely on the book as a companion and adviser, a lifelong loyal friend of our young people who are capable of great things, then we would contribute to bringing up worthy creative young people for the future of our great country.

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